

(RESEARCH ARTICLE)

Evaluation of Technical and Vocational Education Programme of Nigerian Correctional Service Reformatory Institutions in Cross River State

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Abstract

The evaluation of the programmes in the institutions dealing with juvenile offenders in Cross River State is long overdue. This study was patterned on the discrepancy evaluation model aimed at evaluating the technical and vocational Education Training (TVET) programmes for inmates of Nigerian Correctional Service Reformatory Centres in Cross River State. The main thrust of this study is to evaluate the extent to which practices on technical and vocational education and training programme have adhere to; The objectives of the study are to consider the criteria for assigning inmates to different trades, adequacy of curriculum content and facilities. A survey research design was adopted, the total respondents of the study consisted of 394 persons. The total population of 394 was studied, hence no sampling procedure was used. A structured questionnaire with three sections, (A - C) was used as instrument for data collection comprising forty-four items. The items in section A and C were structured on a five-point Likert scale, while section B adopted a check list response type questions of 'YES or NO'. the instrument was pilot tested on 236 respondents who were not part of the population for the study after being subjected to face validation by three experts. The reliability coefficient of the instrument was calculated to be 0.83 using Cronbach Alpha formula. Three research questions and three hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. Frequencies, percentages, mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions, while t-test statistics were employed to test the hypotheses. Among other findings, on the criteria for assigning inmates into technical and vocational areas in the reformatory institutions, the identified four useful criteria usually adopted as interest of the inmates, sex of the inmates, educational background and societal needs. The study equally showed gross inadequacies in the training facilities used for the skill acquisition needs of the inmates (representing 33.33%). Findings of the study showed quite a number of instructional techniques are used for instruction in the reformatory institutions to include among others individualized instruction, demonstrations and questions techniques. Based on these findings' recommendations were made among others that interest of the inmates should be considered seriously in assigning them into technical and vocational areas, the idea is to ensure that the inmates do not abandon training due to disgust and boredom. Previous technical and vocational experience or job was equally recommended, this was to tailor training to the needs, aptitudes and abilities of the inmates.

Keywords: Reformatory Institution; Inmates; Technical and Vocational Training; Evaluation

1. Introduction

All human societies have social problems and they usually attempt to eliminate or reduce such problems. This is done to ensure a healthier social climate in which people can effectively pursue their legitimate individual vocations as well as their collective goals (Labo, 2004). Every society is governed by an acceptable code of conduct or social norms, expressed or understood. These social norms specify what the members of the given society should or should not do. Due to differences in human psychological traits, one is bound to come across some whose behaviours are against the societal norms and laws, while other remain law abiding members. Perhaps, this is the reason why every society deems

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it necessary to have measures of dealing effectively with individuals who are socially misfit. The aim is to deter others from such undesirable acts and therefore reforming the offenders. In the case of young adults involved in antisocial behavior like drug addiction, alcoholism, crime, among others, government at various levels have embarked on programmes aimed at reformation and rehabilitation of the offenders in the Nigerian Correctional Service called Reformatory Institutions or Centres.

Reformatory institutions are places where offenders convicted of crime are confined for training and discipline aimed at achieving reformation rather than punishment. Alemika and Chukwuma (2001) opined that the main purpose of reformatory institutions is to provide care, protection, education and vocational skills, with a view to assisting the inmates to assume socially constructive and productive roles in the society upon release. This is in accordance with the United Nation's Standard Minimum Rules for the treatment of young offenders which stipulated that a child by virtue of his immaturity lack 'Mens Rea' or criminal intent and therefore cannot be held responsible for their offences (Asu-Nandi, 2018). The first prison in Nigeria was established in 1872 in Broad Street, Lagos. There are 227 prisons, 86 satellite prisons and 11 prison farm centres throughout Nigeria. Therefore, considering the number of inmates held in confinement in the various prisons, there is need for the prisons to embark on technical and vocational training programmes for their rehabilitation, to make them 'new creatures on their release. A prison is a place where individuals are physically confined and deprived of a range of personal freedoms.

In Cross River State Nigerian Correctional Service (Nigerian Prison Service) reformatory institutions was established by the federal government in 1962 (Nigerian Prison Service (NPS). The N.P.S explained that the institutions received young offenders from different parts of the country convicted to Borstal training. according to Alemika and Chukwuma (2001) the Act establishing the Borstal institutions and remand centers provides for vocational and educational training as the means of reformatory and rehabilitation of juvenile offenders.

The technical and vocational education training (TVET) programmes of Nigerian Correctional Service Reformatory Centres in Cross River State is intended at equipping the inmates with saleable skills necessary for better living upon release. The programmes are therefore meant to facilitate a smooth re-integration of the inmates into the mainstream of the community. The areas in which vocational training is available in the reformatory institutions as listed by Asu-Nandi (2018) include auto mechanics, tailoring, plumbing, painting and decorating among others. Ambula (2013) vocational training as any training conducted by private or vocational schools intended to develop general or specific skills but not directed to a specific job as it exists in any industry. The principal objectives of TVET programme are the cultivation of work habit and discipline, engagement in production work and acquisition of job skills. Technical and vocational education training programme like every other educational programme are established by government to serve the needs of the individual. More so, funding of educational programmes is expensive and the society wants to see changes in the beneficiaries of educational programme. This lack of positive change seems worse with technical and vocational education training (TVET) programme for the reasons that they are capital intensive and the public complains about their increasingly low-quality graduates. The extent to which the objectives of the educational programme are being achieved can be determined through the process of evaluation.

An evaluation model may be regarded as steps or systems of thinking which if followed or implemented will result in the generation of information which can be used by decision makers in improvement of educational programme. Models provides working vocabulary and defines evaluation tasks. Various quantitative models have been employed in evaluating technical and vocational education training (TVET) programmes among the models include: decision-based model – C.I.P.P., formative model, summative model, discrepancy model, among others.

In the discrepancy model of evaluation, Provus (1969) emphasis on identifying the discrepancy between programme standards and programme performance. The discrepancy information is to identify the weakness of the programme, this information would serve to facilitate the implementation of evaluation findings. Due to the fact that TVET programme of the Nigerian Correctional Service Reformatory Institutions have been planned and implemented, and have been put to use, the essence of evaluation at this stage is to determine the discrepancy that exist between the programmes standards and programme performance, hence discrepancy model shall be adopted for this study.

Programme evaluation as defined by Okoro (2006) is a form of applied research in which specific information relating to a single educational programme or set of programmes are collected. Such information is used for the purpose of solving problems facing the educational institution, programme or course. Programme evaluation provides information on the characteristics of a specific instructional area or course (Okoro, 2006). Once a general structure or system has been developed showing the interaction between components, a working model may be developed to guide the evaluation process. Programme evaluation leads to programme improvement. Since the ultimate goal of the training programme is to help inmates become self-sustaining, disciplined and independent within the law by strengthening

their resources (Onu, 2002), it therefore calls for effective training to enable the inmates become useful to themselves upon release. This will reduce recidivism – the act of being arrested and convicted repeatedly for committing crime.

Ma'aji (2003) in stressing the importance of effective training programme for inmates of reformatory as a people changing institution opined that the society would become a safer place to live as their energies would be diverted to useful ventures. Therefore, for an improvement of the technical and vocational training programme for inmates of reformatory institutions in meeting their marketable skill needs an urgent evaluation becomes necessary, having noticed the apparent failures in turning out law abiding citizens.

1.1. Statement of the Problem

The technical and vocational education training (TVET) programme offered at the Nigerian Correctional Service Reformatory Institutions in Cross River State seem to be grossly inadequate. There are no laid down criteria for assigning inmates to the available TVET trades. The necessary facilities like tools, machines and equipment are either inadequate or virtually non-existent. Moreover, the curriculum content of the programme adopted seems to be inappropriate. All these culminate in the lack of interest or poor attitudes of the inmates in learning the trades. Consequently, what is obvious in such circumstance according to Labo (2004) is increased incidence of recidivism resulting from unemployability of discharged offenders due to lack of saleable skills. The ultimate goal of Nigerian Correctional Service Reformatory Institutions is to help inmates become self-sustaining, disciplined and independent within the law by strengthening all their resources as reported by Onu (2002). Since what is currently obtainable at this point is to the contrary, and more so, with seemingly no record of programme evaluation, an evaluation of Technical and Vocational Education Training (TVET) programme of Nigerian Correctional Service Reformatory Institutions in Cross River State would assist in solving these problems.

1.2. Purpose of the Study

This research sought to evaluate Technical and Vocational Education Training (TVET) programme of Inmates of Nigerian Correctional Service Reformatory Institutions in Cross River State. The specific objectives are to determine:

- The extent in which Nigerian Correctional Service Reformatory Institutions adhere to criteria for assigning inmates into technical and vocational education training programme.
- The extent of adequacy of facilities, tools and equipment for technical and vocational education training programme.
- The extent of adequacy of curriculum content for technical and vocational education programme.

1.3. Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study:

- What are the criteria for assigning inmates of reformatory institutions into various TVET programme?
- How adequate are the training facilities, tools and equipment for TVET programme?
- How relevant are the curriculum content for TVET programme?

1.4. Hypothesis

The following hypotheses relative to the study were tested at 0.05 level of significance

- **Ho₁:** There is no significant difference between the mean responses of instructors and inmates of the reformatory institutions on the criteria for assigning inmates into various TVET programmes.
- **Ho₂:** There is no significant different between the mean responses of instructors and inmates on the adequacy of training facilities in reformatory institutions.
- **Ho₃:** There is no significant different between the mean responses of instructors and inmates on the relevance of the curriculum content of reformatory institutions.

2. Methodology

This study adopted an evaluative research design. According to Nworgu (2006), evaluation research deals with the systematic and comprehensive setting of the most utilitarian or worthwhile goals and the most efficient ways of combining and applying resources for complete actualization of the goals of a given programme. This design is most appropriate to be used for this research because it is assessing the implementation of policies thereby making

judgments about its compliance with the standard set. This research was conducted in Cross River State, which comprised of three senatorial districts with a total of six prisons formations. The reformatory institutions include: Obudu Prison, Ogoja Prison, Ikom Prison, Obubra Prison, Adim Prison and Calabar Prison. The population of this study consisted of 985 respondents in six prisons formations in Cross River State. The study included all Inmates and instructors of Obudu Prison, Ogoja Prison, Ikom Prison, Obubra Prison, Adim Prison and Calabar Prison, the inmates are in their second and third year of training. The reason being that they would have made choices of the trade based on interest. This study adopted the multi-stage proportionate sampling techniques from a total population of 985. According to Akem (2012), the multi-stage proportionate sampling is used when the distribution of the target people cut across a set of groups. In this research, a sample fraction of 40% of the population shall be use in line with the sampling guide provided by Nwanna (1981). Sample fraction of 40% can be used on a population that is in thousands and below while 10% can be used for population that runs into millions. In this research, two Nigerian correctional service reformatory centers out of six shall make up the first stage of sampling and 394 respondents shall be sample from the total population of 985.

In this research, a structured questionnaire was employed as the survey instrument for data collection. The questionnaire items were generated based on the research questions and were designed to elicit information from the inmates, instructors and principal officers of the reformatory institutions. The questionnaire was divided into three sections (A - C) with 44 items.

- Section A – Criteria for Assigning Inmates
- Section B – instructional Facilities, Tools and Equipment
- Section C – Curriculum Contents.

To ensure the validity of the instrument, it was face validated by presenting the initial draft of the instruments to three experts. Two of the experts came from the Department of Industrial Technical Education of University of Nigeria, Nsukka and one from Department of Measurement and Evaluation University of Calabar, Calabar. Specifically, those experts were requested to examine the instrument with respect to the extent the instrument will measure the current practices in technical and vocational education training programme of Nigerian correctional service reformatory institutions. Their comments, suggestions and corrections were used to modify the instrument and arrive at the final work. To determine the reliability of questionnaire, the scores of the 40 respondents in the trial testing instruments was used to establish the internal consistency reliability using the Cronbach Alpha Method.

The TVETQ was administered to the respondents by the Lead Researcher, Co-Researcher and 8 Research Assistants. The personal contact and on-the-spot collection were to ensure a high rate of participation of the subjects and optimum return of the instrument. However, where the completed questionnaire cannot be collected on the spot, a repeat visit was made. Data obtained for the research was analysis using mean, standard deviation, percentage and t-test statistics. The responses from the questionnaire items (A and C) were analyzed using 5-point Likert scale by assigning 5,4,3,2, and 1 point respectively with the average point of 3.00. since the upper limit of 3.00 is 3.50, the items whose mean scores are 3.50 and above were regarded as agreed and below as disagreed. While section B which employed check list response type questions of 'YES' or 'NO', frequencies and percentages were used to determine the level of acceptance or otherwise. Fifty percent and above was regarded as adequate while below as inadequate. In testing the null hypotheses, the calculated t-test value (t-cal) was compared with the table value (t-table) at 0.05 level of significant. This t-test of significant helped to determine the degree of difference in the responses of the respondents (inmates, instructors and principal officers) from the hypotheses stated. Where the t-calculated value exceeds the t-table value, the null hypothesis (H_0) is rejected, while the alternative hypothesis (H_1) is upheld meaning that there is significant difference. On the other hand, where the t-calculated value is less than the t-table value, the null hypothesis (H_0) is upheld, this indicates that there is no significant difference in their responses.

3. Results

3.1. Research Question 1

What are the criteria for assigning inmates of reformatory institutions into various TVET trades?

Table 1 above revealed that out of 12-items on the criteria for assigning inmates into trades four have mean range of 3.94 to 4.76 and least standard deviation of 0.43. It therefore means that four out of the 12 possible criteria listed are the ones the instructors and inmates identified as generally useful for assigning inmates to various occupational trades. This is because the four items were above the cut-off point of 3.50.

Table 1 Mean and standard deviations of responses of instructors and inmates on the criteria for assigning inmates of reformatory institutions into various TVET trades

S/N	Criteria for Assigning Inmates into TVET Trades	\bar{X}	SD	Remark
1.	Age of inmates is considered in assigning them into various TVET trades	1.85	0.64	Disagreed
2.	Inmates are allowed to choose their TVET based on their interest	3.95	0.74	Agreed
3.	Parental opinion is considered in placing inmates into relevant occupational trade to enhance their reformation and rehabilitation.	2.02	0.08	Disagreed
4.	The sex of inmates determined their TVET placement	3.94	0.73	Agreed
5.	Simple random technique is used to assign inmates into various TVET trades	2.91	1.14	Disagreed
6.	Inmates aptitudes are always considered before assigning them to TVET trades.	2.20	0.78	Disagreed
7.	Religious inclination is a yardstick for assigning inmates into various TVET trades.	1.92	0.43	Disagreed
8.	Societal need greatly determined the TVET placement of the inmates	4.13	0.45	Agreed
9.	Inmates are assigned into TVET trades based on their previous TVET background (if any).	4.76	0.43	Agreed
10.	Instructors used their description for assigning inmates into various vocation.	1.66	1.23	Disagreed
11.	Health condition of inmates determined their vocational placement.	1.70	1.30	Disagreed
12.	Cultural background of the inmates determined their occupational placement	1.71	1.29	Disagreed

3.2. Research Question 2

How adequate are the training facilities tools and equipment in the reformatory institutions meeting the skill needs of the inmates?

Table 2 Frequency and percentages on the adequacy of the training facilities, tools and equipment in the reformatory institutions for meeting the skills needs of the inmates

S/N	Training Facilities, tools and equipment	Recommended Standard	Yes		No		Total	Rmks
			F	%	F	%		
13.	Consumable materials (wood, metal, cables, etc.)	Readily available for practical	94	26.86	300	71.14	394	I
14	Location of toilet facilities	Provided within the workshop complex or adjacent to the workshop	99	25.13	295	74.87	394	I
15.	Number of classroom available	Each trade allocated at least one classroom	29	7.36	365	92.64	394	I
16.	Toilet facilities for males and females	Separate toilet for males and females	250	63.45	144	36.55	394	A
17.	Classroom space	At least 1.7m ² of classroom space for inmates	200	50.76	194	49.24	394	A
18.	Seats for inmates in the classroom	According to inmates' number	140	35.53	254	64.47	394	I
19.	Chalkboard in classrooms	At least 3m ² in size	295	74.87	99	25.13	394	A
20.	Number of workshop available	Workshop for each trade	59	14.97	335	85.00	394	I

21.	Instructor office enclosure	Partly covered with class to enable him/her see all activities going on in the workshop	74	18.78	320	82.23	394	I
22.	Storage space in workshop for inmates' projects or display room	At least 5% additional space	220	55.84	174	44.16	394	A
23.	Chalkboard in the workshop	At least 3m ²	299	75.89	95	24.11	394	A
24.	Common hand tools	Readily available for inmates for practical	194	49.24	200	50.76	394	I
25.	Testing equipment/instrument	Readily available for inmates for practical	192	48.73	202	51.27	394	I
26.	Drawing equipment	Enough for 30 - 40 inmates	154	39.09	240	60.91	394	I
27.	Holding tools (bench vice, etc.)	Enough for 30 - 40 inmates	180	45.69	214	54.31	394	I

Key: A – Adequate

3.2.1. I – Inadequate

A set of 15 items in table 2 above were used to gather information from instructors and inmates on the adequacy of training facilities, tools and equipment in the reformatory institutions. The table shows the frequencies and percentages of the respondents. Out of the 15 items presented, five are above the acceptance level of 50% and above, meaning that only items 16,17,19,22 and 23 are adequate, while the remaining ten falls below the cut-off level of 50%. This therefore means that items 13, 14, 15, 18, 20, 21, 24, 25, 26 and 27 are inadequate for skill acquisition training of the inmates in the reformatory institutions of Cross River State representing only 33.33%.

3.3. Research Question 3

How relevant are the curriculum contents and instructional techniques used in various TVET trades?

Table 3 Mean and standard deviation of the responses of the instructors on the relevant of the curriculum contents and instructional techniques used in various occupational trades

NB: Inmates were exempted from items 28 – 44

S/N	Necessary conditions in teaching TVET trades	\bar{X}	SD	Remarks
28.	The subjects have enough practical components	3.74	1.39	Agreed
29.	The subjects center on the development of skills that inmates need for self-employment	4.08	1.20	Agreed
30.	The subjects have both theory and practical sub-units	3.87	1.25	Agreed
31.	The content of the training programme is relevant to the reformatory environment	3.76	1.19	Agreed
32.	Curriculum content is revised to meet the present need of inmates and the society	3.78	1.09	Agreed
33.	The training programme reflects the need of the society	4.08	0.85	Agreed
34.	Individualized instructional technique is used for instruction	3.87	1.18	Agreed
35.	Demonstration method is used in instruction for specific skill	4.74	0.62	Agreed
36.	Demonstrations are always on real jobs using real materials	3.87	1.18	Agreed
37.	Learning tasks are discussed with inmates before instruction	4.43	0.08	Agreed
38.	Instructors prepare their training activities to teach the inmates skills	4.09	2.20	Agreed
39.	Inmates acquire saleable skills that would enable them to be self-reliant or get job upon release	4.13	0.81	Agreed
40.	Appropriate instructional materials are usually available for instruction	2.04	1.19	Disagreed
41.	Inmates are free to ask questions during classroom or workshop activities	4.00	1.13	Agreed

42.	Sequential operation of projects or job are explained in the workshop	3.87	1.18	Agreed
43.	Instructors give practical assignment to inmates in group	3.65	1.35	Agreed
44.	Instructors give definite instruction when moving from one instructional area to another	3.61	1.34	Agreed

The mean rating in table 3 above shows that 16 out of 17 items were rated above agreed cut-off mark of 3.50, while only 1 item falls below. The item that did not reach the cut-off mark fell within the disagreed category, with mean ratings between 2.04 and standard deviation of 1.19.

3.3.1. Hypothesis 1

- H_{01} : There is no significant difference between the mean responses of instructors and inmates of the reformatory institutions on the criteria for assigning inmates into various TVET trades.

Table 4 t-Test comparison of mean responses of the instructors and inmates on the criteria for assigning inmates of reformatory institutions into various TVET trades

S/N	\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	t-cal	Remarks
1.	3.96	0.88	3.94	0.75	1.07	NS
2.	3.96	0.89	3.95	0.75	1.05	NS
3.	2.22	1.38	2.06	0.76	0.53	NS
4.	4.04	0.37	3.94	0.75	1.04	NS
5.	2.13	0.34	2.10	1.15	0.32	NS
6.	2.22	0.67	2.10	0.57	0.84	NS
7.	2.00	0.43	1.91	0.43	0.92	NS
8.	4.22	0.42	4.15	0.83	0.84	NS
9.	4.83	0.39	4.75	0.43	0.95	NS
10.	2.22	1.54	1.63	1.20	1.80	NS
11.	1.13	1.34	1.07	0.26	0.83	NS
12.	2.52	1.68	1.65	1.22	2.44	S

Note: $N_1 = 23$, $N_2 = 371$, $df = n_1 + n_2 - 2 = 392$, $t_{392} (0.05) = 1.97$., NS = Not Significant, S = Significant

The result of table 4 above shows the opinion of the respondents (instructors and inmates) on the criteria for assigning inmates into various TVET trades. It can be seen that t-calculated values of eleven items (i.e. 1,2,3,4,5,6,7,8,9,10 and 11) were less than the table value while only item 12 was above. Therefore, the null hypothesis was upheld for each of the 11 items, while the null hypothesis was rejected for only item 12. Consequently, it can be stated categorically that the opinions of the respondents did not differ on the eleven items but differ in one only.

3.3.2. Hypothesis 2

- H_{02} : There is no significant different between the mean responses of instructors and inmates on the adequacy of training facilities in reformatory institutions.

In table 5 above it shows that the opinion of the respondents regarding the adequacy of training facilities, tools and equipment for inmates of reformatory institutions. The opinion of the respondents did not differ on all the 15 items. As a result, the null hypotheses are upheld since t-calculated were all less than the t-value. Based on this, the null hypothesis: there is no significant difference between the mean responses of instructors and inmates on the adequacy of training facilities, tools and equipment in reformatory institutions is thereby upheld.

Table 5 t-Test comparison of the mean responses of instructors and inmates on the adequacy of training facilities, tools and equipment in reformatory institutions.

S/N	\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	t-Cal	Remarks
13.	2.00	0.43	1.91	0.43	0.92	NS
14.	4.22	0.42	4.15	0.83	0.84	NS
15.	4.83	0.39	4.75	0.43	0.95	NS
16.	2.22	1.54	1.63	1.20	1.80	NS
17.	1.13	1.34	1.07	0.26	0.83	NS
18.	3.96	0.88	3.94	0.75	1.07	NS
19.	2.22	1.38	2.06	0.76	0.53	NS
20.	4.04	0.37	3.94	0.75	1.04	NS
21.	3.96	0.89	3.95	0.75	1.05	NS
22.	2.13	0.34	2.10	1.15	0.32	NS
23.	2.22	0.67	2.10	0.57	0.84	NS
24.	4.78	0.43	4.70	0.46	0.85	NS
25.	1.26	0.45	1.16	0.37	0.04	NS
26.	1.83	0.39	1.79	0.41	0.48	NS
27.	2.00	0.74	1.97	0.44	0.08	NS

Note: $N_1 = 23, N_2 = 371, df = n_1 + n_2 - 2 = 392, t_{392} (0.05) = 1.97$; NS = Not Significant, S = Significant

3.3.3. Hypothesis 3

- Ho3: There is no significant different between the mean responses of instructors and inmates on the relevance of the curriculum content of reformatory institutions.

Table 6 t-Test comparison of the mean responses of instructors and inmates on the relevance of the curriculum contents of reformatory institutions

S/N	\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	t-Cal	Remarks
28.	3.96	0.88	3.94	0.75	1.07	NS
29.	1.83	0.39	1.79	0.41	0.48	NS
30.	4.04	0.37	3.94	0.75	1.04	NS
31.	2.22	1.54	1.63	1.20	1.80	NS
32.	1.13	1.34	1.07	0.26	0.83	NS
33.	3.96	0.88	3.94	0.75	1.07	NS
34.	2.22	1.38	2.06	0.76	0.53	NS
35.	4.83	0.39	4.75	0.43	0.95	NS
36.	3.96	0.89	3.95	0.75	1.05	NS
37.	2.13	0.34	2.10	1.15	0.32	NS
38.	4.04	0.37	3.94	0.75	1.04	NS
39.	4.78	0.43	4.70	0.46	0.85	NS
40.	1.26	0.45	1.16	0.37	0.04	NS

41.	2.22	0.67	2.10	0.57	0.84	NS
42.	4.83	0.39	4.75	0.43	0.95	NS
43.	1.57	0.90	1.39	0.69	0.94	NS
44.	4.43	0.51	4.42	0.51	0.09	NS

Note: $N_1 = 23$, $N_2 = 371$, $df = n_1 + n_2 - 2 = 392$, $t_{392} (0.05) = 1.97$.; NS = Not Significant, S = Significant

In table 6 above it shows that the opinion of the respondents regarding the adequacy of training facilities, tools and equipment for inmates of reformatory institutions. The opinion of the respondents did not differ on all the 17 items. As a result, the null hypotheses are upheld since t-calculated were all less than the t-value. Based on this, the null hypothesis: There is no significant different between the mean responses of instructors and inmates on the relevance of the curriculum content of reformatory institutions is thereby upheld.

4. Discussion

The major findings of the research are discussed inline with the organization of the research questions and hypotheses in this research.

The data analysis presented in Table 1 revealed the criteria for assigning inmates to TVET trades. The criteria, interest of the inmates with response mean rating of 3.95 is an important factor that can influence inmates' choice of occupation. Without considering interest of the inmates there would be no attention which could result in little or no learning taken place. This assertion is inline with Nwachukwu (1998) who suggest that in the choice of vocation, it is important to consider interest of the learner.

The criteria, sex of inmates with mean response rating of 3.54 is an obvious factor in most reformatory institutions in the Northern part of Nigeria. The cultural role expectation of men and women are known to be clearly spelt out. Studies have shown significant relationship between gender and occupational aspiration, preference and choice. This finding is in agreement with the opinion of Labo (2004) who observed that women were socialized and made to be passive and submissive to the male. Thus, that oriented them into considering jobs that were "feminine" and go hand in hand with lesser energy and demanding vocations like carpentry and welding.

The findings also identified societal need as a criterion for assigning inmates to various vocations, the item has a mean response rating of 4.13. This finding supports the opinion of Ambula (2013) who advocated that programme designed for TVET training should be based on accurate need assessment of labour market required of that community. Finally, the findings reveal the criteria, educational background of the inmates (if any), rated highly with 4.76 as response mean concise with suggestions of Alemika and Alemika (1994), who in their recommendations said assigning inmates to TVET training areas should be based on objective criteria and methods such as previous educational attainment, previous TVET training and experience and psychological testing. These criteria they believe would also reduce training difficulties that could be encountered by the instructors.

Table 2 shows items that are above the agreed 50%. The items: separate toilet facilities for males and females, classroom space, chalkboard in classroom and workshops and storage space in workshop for inmates' projects or display room as adequate in accordance with ILO/UNDP recommendations. The table equally revealed the responses on items that are grossly inadequate for TVET training of inmates for skill acquisition. This is because the items fall below the 50% acceptable level. The finding is in consonance with the reports of Alemika & Chukwuma (2001) and Asu-Nandi (2018), who in their different findings lamented gross inadequacies of the training facilities, tools and equipment for the inmates who need to go back to the mainstream of the society.

Table 3 indicates the findings on the instructional techniques used for instruction. The fact that the respondents were able to appreciate the importance of the use of various instructional techniques in TVET trades training programme is quite appreciable. This is in agreement with the views of Asu-Nandi and Ikutal (2015), who contended that acquisition of different types of skills, knowledge, attitude and behavior requires different strategies for teaching it. Undoubtedly, the use of various techniques will motivate the inmates to acquire saleable skills to become useful to themselves and the society upon release. It is worthy to note that the development of interest and attention of inmates will depend largely on the initiative of the instructors and appropriate use of this teaching aids, selection of appropriate methods/techniques for topic or skill he/she wants to teach for maximum result.

A test of significance difference was used to test the hypothesis on the criteria for assigning inmates into various TVET trades. This was shown in Table 4. At a calculated t-value, eleven items were less and one item was more than the critical t-value of 1.97. Therefore, the null hypothesis was upheld for eleven items, while it was rejected for only one item. The significance difference on the item from the respondents might be as a result of individual perception as an instructor or inmate. On the part of the inmates the difference in opinion might be due to their level of awareness and the demand of labour market in the state's studies.

The same t-test significant was used in Table 5 for the second hypothesis on the adequacy of training facilities, tools and equipment for TVET trades training for inmates. All the items were less than the critical t-value, hence the null hypothesis was automatically accepted. There was general agreement between the instructors/teachers and inmates on the training facilities, tools and equipment for training of inmates of reformatory institutions. The respondents expressed inadequacy on training facilities, tools and equipment. If the training facilities, tools and equipment was adequate, the much-needed desire for reforming the skills, knowledge and attitude of the inmates would be achieved.

Table 6 shows the t-test significant for the relevance of the instructional techniques and curriculum content used in various TVET trades. All the items were less than the critical t-value, hence the null hypothesis was automatically accepted. There was general agreement between the teachers/instructors and inmates on the relevance of curriculum contents and instructional techniques used in TVET trades of reformatory institutions. The respondents expressed irrelevancy of curriculum contents and instructional techniques. If the curriculum contents and instructional techniques was relevant, the much-needed desire for reforming the knowledge, attitude and skills of the inmates would be achieved.

5. Conclusion

Based on the findings of the research, it can be deduced that the TVET programme of the reformatory institutions are in a pitifully lackluster affair. There is hardly any conscientious effort made to provide any meaningful TVET training at the reformatory institutions. The goals for establishing the reformatory institutions have been negated as a result of poor state of facilities in the institutions.

However, the instructional and training components (assigning inmates to TVET trades, training facilities, tools and equipment, and curriculum contents and instructional techniques) determined in the research represents a consensual list of what the respondents considered would hinder as well as enhance the acquisition of skills in the reformatory institutions. It is expected that adequately planned and implemented reformatory TVET training programme that is based on the findings of this research will equip the inmates with the necessary skills that help them become self-reliant in the world of work upon discharge. This would in effect help to reduce crime in the society as well as recidivism among the crime conscious members of our society. Hence, conscious positive efforts should in effect be made to enhance the operation of effective Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET) programme available in the reformatory institutions.

Recommendations

The following measures are recommended for improving the TVET training programme for inmates of reformatory institutions in Cross River State for effective reformation, rehabilitation and reintegration of inmates on discharge.

- In assigning inmates into different TVET trades, the interest of the inmates should be considered seriously. The idea is to ensure that the inmates do not abandon training due to disgust and boredom.
- Since the findings of the research revealed gross inadequacies of training facilities, tools and equipment, efforts should be intensified by administrators and those concerned with the handling of the inmates in soliciting fund from philanthropists, local or international organizations among others.
- For effective and functional instruction, instructional techniques and curriculum contents identified in this research should not be used in isolation, but in pairs

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

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